

WAYS TO INCREASE ORAL AND WRITTEN SPEECH OF STUDENTS IN LITERATURE TEXTBOOKS

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Abstract: This scientific article provides information on ways to improve students' oral and written speech in literature textbooks.

Key words: oral speech, written speech, internal speech, external speech, physiological, psychological.

Literature classes have great opportunities for developing students' oral and written speech. Here is literary reading, expressive reading, interpreting the text, memorizing, retelling, planning the text, extracting a separate part of the work, finding titles for untitled works (in particular, lyrical works in our classical literature), identifying the author or characters of the work. There are different types of work, such as writing letters, writing reviews of literary works or literary-critical articles. In this regard, it is necessary to study speech in the following ways.

1. Spoken speech is a conversational speech with a normal sound, and this speech is expressed with more tones and various gestures.
2. Written speech is realized through the combination of letters and words based on certain rules, punctuation marks, various separations: paragraphs, paragraphs.
3. Internal speech is a passive speech of a person, which does not require the participation of a second person.
4. External speech is active speech directed at others and controllable. With the help of speech, a person expresses his thoughts, feelings, desires and understands the thoughts, feelings, and desires of others. Speech is oral and written. Oral speech is the usual spoken speech, and this speech is more related to tone and various gestures. Complex grammatical devices and conjunctions are hardly used in it. First of all, it should be noted that all subjects taught at school are aimed at working on the student's speech. The science of mother tongue is the most basic and important among them. One of the main factors for the development of students' oral and written speech culture is regular monitoring of students' speech by all subject teachers at school. Naturally, this work starts from primary school, and Uzbek language and literature teachers play an important role in this. Different environments have a strong influence on the psyche and speech of children. In some families, parents, educators in

kindergartens, and teachers in primary schools have a positive influence on children's speech - children acquire the skills of cultural and literary speech. Due to the neglect of this issue in some families, kindergartens and schools, the child is deprived of acquiring cultural speech. This situation has a negative impact on the child's growth and development as a culturally mature person, of course. Therefore, it is necessary to pay great attention to the development of speech skills in a child from a young age.

A literature teacher develops literary speech by teaching students a work of art. The peculiarity of the development of students' speech in literature classes is that the teacher develops the skills of reading, memorizing, and expressive speaking of artistic works in the class by improving their grammatical rules, word count. achieves that they acquire the laws of language, develops their literary speech. The development of students' oral and written speech culture depends on the quality of literature teaching. At the same time, the development of speech culture requires the organization of activities such as lexical exercises, retelling, narration, and essay. Special exercises for the development of speech in literature classes are held throughout the literature course. In developing students' oral and written skills, attention is paid not only to making a plan, briefly recording the content, writing a statement, and an essay, but also to their reading and life experiences. Developing students' speech is a long process. It is impossible to achieve good and high-quality education, students' acquisition of cultural speech, if training related to speech development cannot be conducted consistently and continuously. Accordingly, it is one of the important tasks of the teacher to improve the development of speech in the lesson, to continue the work of primary grades with the work of middle grades, and to continue the work of middle grades with the work carried out in higher grades.

Cultivating speech culture is not only a long-term process, but also a creative process. This process requires an independent creative approach to the essay and oral narration. Therefore, to arouse interest in the correct pronunciation of words in students, to give written and oral speech, to answer questions, to write statements and essays, to strengthen and develop their acquired knowledge and skills in this field, It is necessary to develop the ability to work independently. The following principles are the basis of teaching oral speech:

- ❖ *relying on conscious perception and creative repetition of linguistic material of information;*
- ❖ *connection with life and literature as a subject of study;*
- ❖ *listening, speaking, reading and writing relationships;*

- ❖ *continuity of logical, semantic and pronunciation content of body parts of oral speech;*
- ❖ *arousing interest in news speech material, content and form of speech;*

These principles assume the leading role of the teacher in the process of teaching students, determine the content of teaching oral speech, its material, teaching methods, and take into account their abilities. Mother tongue students, the interest of children, shows the need for modern use of technical tools, the development of speech requires that the students' level of knowledge of grammar is not delayed. The development of students' oral speech is understood as teaching them to speak in the conditions of listening and speaking. Perception of foreign speech by ear is associated with a number of difficulties. One of them is the phrasing of the flow of speech, so even knowledge of its lexical units does not guarantee understanding of the thought in a coherent text.

In addition, the oral material known to students during reading may not always be correctly perceived by the ear due to differences in sound and visual verbal images. Listening, or as it is called "listening, is a more difficult method of obtaining information compared to reading", which in physiological and psychological research determines the characteristics of auditory reception of speech: reception of sounds - words - phrases. different times when listening, at the same time - when reading; Fatigue when receiving speech by hearing is more than visual and others. Perception of speech is also affected by the speed at which it is spoken, the presence or absence of visual aids. If the student sees the speaker, observes his articulation, the student's speech organs seem to correspond to him, it becomes easier to repeat the sounds and words heard in his inner speech. These difficulties are eliminated through a special system of exercises to develop listening skills, as well as in the implementation of others in addition to listening.

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